

Student Apathy: Survey Analysis of Poca High School and a Review of Current Literature

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Abstract

Student apathy (disengagement, low motivation, and lack of purpose) is a growing concern in education. However, research shows it stems from deeper issues such as passive teaching methods, limited student choice, and academic struggles. To determine whether these issues are universal, psychology students at Poca High School created and implemented the Disengagement Observation Tracking Survey (DOTS) used in this study. Results indicate minimal change in student attitudes toward education, as self-reported views of assessment and instruction mirror the initial findings of the literature review.

Keywords: apathy, passive learning, instruction, academic struggle, purpose

Introduction

Student apathy is a growing concern in education. In an article from the *Journal of Agricultural Education*, authors DeLay and Swan state that most students interviewed in a 2014 study identified “mediocre teaching” and “archaic assessments” as a factor in their apathy toward school. The research indicates that these factors can create a learning atmosphere where an “absence of learning purpose” exists (DeLay & Swan, 2014). Yacek & Jonas support this position by stating that when students “fail to acknowledge, accept, and [...] embrace the struggle of education,” “apathy, disengagement, and even resentment” are often the result because learning becomes “something to be avoided [or] endured” (2019). To determine whether increased access to technology and post-pandemic changes to education have addressed these issues, psychology students at Poca High School created and implemented the Disengagement Observation Tracking Survey (DOTS) used in this study. Results indicate minimal change in student attitudes toward education, as self-reported views of assessment and instruction mirror the initial findings of the literature review.

Methods

After reviewing the data and disposing of surveys that appeared to be incomplete, dual-enrolled psychology students from Poca, conducting this study on student apathy, were left with a total of 92 surveys out of a total of 410 students currently enrolled. This 92:410 ratio roughly calculated to be about 20% of Poca High School’s student body. Participants involved in this study were not contacted directly for recruitment and instead were granted permission to participate in our educational study by teachers and administration via email. A script was

prepared and read aloud to each class that provided students with baseline information and instructions on how to proceed after the completion of their survey. Following the script's conclusion, students interested in contributing to our research by sharing their honest opinions about their personal experiences at school, by means of a survey, were asked to raise their hand. Students with their hands raised were handed an 8-item questionnaire containing a variety of questions that correlated to the three subcategories of apathy: purpose, academic struggle, and instruction.

The newly designed survey was dubbed the “Disengagement Observation Tracking Survey” (or DOTS survey) as it was designed specifically for Poca High School. Our intent when developing this survey was to assess high school students on their level of apathy and compare the schools' average with studies of similar content. This study derives its credibility by utilizing resources through ERIC (Education Resources Information Center) and through previously release surveys including The Identification with School Questionnaire (Voelkl, 1997), The Psychological Sense of School Membership Scale (Goodenow, 1993), and The School Success Profile (Bowen, et al., 2003). Although participants were kept anonymous on paper, while conducting the experiment, psychology students stood there in the room and noticed that the majority of research participants were predominantly white, middle-class, high school students either identifying as male or female within grades 9–12. Upon analyzing the responses, it was found that GPA and attendance were also factors that influenced the results.

Review of Current Literature

Concerns about the levels of student apathy are increasing nationwide. Current research indicates that self-purpose is a contributing factor to student engagement, and is a powerful counter to student apathy. Student apathy—defined as a lack of interest, motivation, and

engagement from students toward school and learning—can be improved by identifying self-purpose, allowing students to achieve a sense of motivation, learning drive, and understanding regarding their education. This can be achieved through several methods, including setting long-term goals for students and allowing them to have more choice in their learning.

Multiple components contribute to the growing pandemic of student apathy, and a strong sense of purpose is among the most crucial. Student choice is a necessary factor for students to retain information and to provide them with a sense of educational fulfillment. “Students who are given choices and some control over their own learning naturally feel more empowered within the classroom and gain a deeper connection to the learning they are doing” (Fordyce, 2024). If students can choose what they learn and how they learn it, they will engage with content that interests and benefits them in the most efficient way. This allows students to see more purpose in learning. By allowing choice, students can gain a better understanding of the material they are consuming and the reasons behind their learning, which increases their chances of academic success.

“Self-directed approaches emphasize personal satisfaction and curiosity [...] student-led investigations can enhance engagement and learning outcomes” (Foxworthy, et al., 2025). By setting an end goal in the learning process, students have something to strive for and become more self-motivated, pushing them to become more engaged in their education. Often, there is no perceived purpose in doing something without an end goal—so why would students feel motivated to engage in education if they don’t see a meaningful outcome? Research indicates that these factors can create a learning atmosphere where an “absence of learning purpose” exists (DeLay & Swan, 2014). “It is posited that individuals tend to orient themselves towards their purposes via setting long-term overarching goals” (Alderson, et al., 2025). By achieving these

goals, students gain a sense of pride, success, and accomplishment, motivating them to continue their efforts.

Finding students' sense of purpose and fulfillment are "important initiatives to promote their educational purpose, joy of learning, and overall subjective well-being," according to Gitima Sharma and Mariya A. Yukhymenko-Lescroart of California State University (2022). Small adjustments in a student's learning environment, such as offering more choice, can positively impact their educational experience and reduce apathy worldwide. By setting long-term goals and offering greater student choice, educators give students the chance to find their sense of purpose. Schools must use their capacity to foster students' self-purpose through these strategies to encourage more motivated and attentive attitudes toward learning.

Academic struggle is one of the leading causes of student apathy across the globe. Both external and internal factors contribute to this issue. Metacognition is "one's thinking of his own thinking" (McGuire, 2021) and is useful in showing students how to learn. Environmental factors are crucial to student learning each day; in a high-quality environment, students feel comfortable and are more likely to produce quality work. Accountability also plays a role. Without it, students may face motivational issues that lead to low attendance. Yacek and Jonas support this position by stating that when students "fail to acknowledge, accept, and [...] embrace the struggle of education," "apathy, disengagement, and even resentment" are often the result, because learning becomes "something to be avoided [or] endured" (2019). These attendance problems can result in confusion and academic failure. Metacognition, accountability, and environment are all major elements contributing to academic struggle.

Metacognitive strategies reduce the gap between students who struggle and those who thrive. McGuire (2021) notes, "Metacognitive strategies such as reflection, self-questioning, and

analyzing one's strengths and weaknesses allow an individual to more effectively use cognitive strategies." Many schools, including Poca High School, use cognitive learning as a primary instructional strategy. Since metacognitive strategies enhance cognitive abilities, integrating them into daily instruction would be highly beneficial.

Higher-order thinking skills (HOTS) also play a vital role in developing critical thinking and problem-solving. Mitani (2021) states, "The public education system has a critical role in supporting students' acquisition of HOTS because these skills can be enhanced through student-centered instruction. [...] 60% of Americans think that public schools should have a vast responsibility for ensuring that future workers have the right skills to succeed in today's and future economy." By combining HOTS and cognitive abilities, students can improve their metacognitive skills. Enhanced cognitive abilities through metacognition improve HOTS performance and critical thinking, which benefits students in both academic and real-life situations. For example, debates can help students analyze multiple perspectives and develop deeper understanding.

Environmental factors and accountability also influence student struggles. Found that "Home/family, school environment, classmates/peers, community, media, and technology were not significantly affecting the performance of the students," (Penconcillo, et al., 2020), but Laing (2020) argues that "the obvious reason for the failure to solve the retention/attrition problem is that the concept of providing a blended learning environment is inherently complex and ignores the fact that all students do not learn in the same way." Later, Penconcillo acknowledged that attendance was the primary cause of student struggle at that school (2020).

While both factors are significant, the learning environment may be more influential. Many students struggle with attendance, but more are affected by their learning environments.

Creating an environment that suits most students could help reduce apathy. Accountability is also important. Students can take responsibility for their learning. Cherry and Coleman (n.d.) state, “The individual student assumes responsibility for taking action to complete the required steps which will ultimately bring [a] plan to fruition.” Although this plan was designed for college students dismissed for academic deficiency, it could still be useful for others. Students who must retake classes could create their own plans with goals, giving them accountability, purpose, and choice. For example, students who fall behind could be allowed to choose a time to complete their work. If they show no responsibility, consequences should follow.

Student apathy is more common among secondary students accustomed to passive learning. Children are conditioned to be passive learners as early as elementary school through teacher-led instruction where students mostly observe or take notes. Writing in the *Journal of Agricultural Education*, DeLay and Swan note that most students interviewed in their 2014 study identified “mediocre teaching” and “archaic assessments” as driving factors in their apathy toward school. Research shows that these methods can hinder critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and overall engagement and motivation (Goel, 2024).

Several modern studies suggest solutions to this global issue. Schools that provide a more engaging environment—through discussions, group work, and hands-on projects—are more likely to foster student interest (Goel, 2024). Researchers observed a significant increase in student involvement following changes in teaching methods. One student wrote anonymously, “I feel that the teacher is very dedicated in class and interacts with us. This creates an active atmosphere in class” (Pan, 2024). Students noted that the new lessons helped them both academically and in how they viewed the relevance of what they were learning (Adil, et al.,

2021). Positive teacher–student relationships also lead to better outcomes, as students who feel supported experience lower levels of anxiety and boredom (Furlong, et al., 2021).

Results

Survey data revealed that 1 in 10 people out of the 20% of Poca High’s population surveyed saw no purpose or value in their time at Poca High School. This lack of purpose directly correlates with student apathy. The data shows that 10% of students see no future value in their education, and 9% don't believe that skills learned at Poca high school will ever benefit them moving forward. This could be due to the lack of long-term goals set during school. Aiding in goal setting for the student population would allow students to see how the work being done currently will contribute to their goals and allow them to achieve in the future. According to the data 50% of students reported a lack of choice regarding their education, which is also crucial for developing a sense of purpose.

Concerning instruction, 60% of students indicated that their talents and abilities are not well measured by classroom assessments. Active learning is shown to counter student apathy by fostering deeper engagement and motivation. A desire for assessments that are engaging and relevant indicates interest in a supportive environment where students feel valued. The benefits of incorporating such active learning extends beyond engagement by actively combating student apathy. While 75% of students reported feeling challenged by their coursework, the remaining 25% did not report feeling challenged or developing new ideas.

After analyzing the survey, the results suggested that one in three (30%) students quit when they feel behind or confused. Yacek and Jonas state that learning can become “something to be avoided [or] endured.” When students feel this way, it can cause motivational and attendance issues. Attendance issues can cause more confusion. Instead of enduring work that is causing uncertainty, they avoid it. If 1 in 3 students are avoiding their work, that means in a 20-student-classroom, 6 or 7 students are avoiding assignments. Those students that are not doing their tasks are potentially influencing other students to also not partake in their work, which can cause more student apathy in schools.

49% of PHS students also feel that their opinions and personal input are neither wanted

nor needed. This feeling can strongly affect the students' motivation, as well as their overall learning. Laing supports this by saying "the obvious reason for the failure to solve the retention/attrition problem is that the concept of providing a blended learning environment is inherently complex and ignores the fact that all students do not learn in the same way." This suggests that half of the students at PHS may have increased problems with their education, due to their perception that their school environment and administration do not care about their personal learning styles and opinions.

74% of students say that classes challenge them to think and form new opinions, while a quarter feels that their classes do not. Though most students do feel challenged, there is still a prevalent number of students who feel the opposite. McGuire (2021) notes, "Metacognitive strategies such as reflection, self-questioning, and analyzing one's strengths and weaknesses allow an individual to more effectively use cognitive strategies." As expressed previously, PHS uses cognitive strategies frequently in their coursework. This piece of literature implies that the students who do not feel challenged may not have been exposed to or are lacking in metacognitive strategies.

Discussion

The alarming revelation that nearly 75% of students do not view grades as an indicator of intelligence, coupled with the 60% who do not believe their abilities are accurately measured by current assessments and assignments, indicates an obvious need for further inquiry. Which

assessments are lacking? Are respondents dissatisfied with standardized testing, or with instruction in general? Why are grades considered a poor measure of ability? Clearly, follow-up questions should be focused on the specifics of these views. Direct discussions between teachers and students may also provide insight, although students may struggle to articulate the impetus of their perspective on grading and assessment.

Additional research into best practices is also needed to address the 30% of students who admit they “quit trying” when they are confused or behind in their assignments. The negative influence that these students bring into the classroom must be addressed both to increase their likelihood of success and to mitigate the possibility of it influencing others. Increased rapport, intervention programs, or other school-based solutions will be necessary to identify struggling students. Once identified, actions to remedy or prevent apathetic behaviors can be implemented.

References

- Adil, A., Lee, K., & Dietiker, L. (n.d.). RELEVANCE AS PERCEIVED BY HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS IN DECONTEXTUALIZED MATHEMATICS LESSONS. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED630444.pdf>
- Alderson, Jacob E, et al. "Sense of Purpose in Life Predicts University Performance and Attrition." *Student Success*, vol. 16, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.5204/ssj.3612>. Accessed 2 Oct. 2025.
- Bowen, G. L., Richman, J. M., Bowen, N. K., & Broughton, A. (2003). The School Success Profile Online. *Journal of Technology in Human Services*, 21(1-2), 111–138. https://doi.org/10.1300/j017v21n01_06
- Cherry, L., & Coleman, L. (n.d.). A Plan for Academic Success: Helping Academically Dismissed Students Achieve their Goals. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ907797.pdf>
- De Lay, A., & Swan, B. (2014). Student Apathy As Defined By Secondary Agricultural Education Students. *Journal of Agricultural Education*, 55(1), 106–119. <https://doi.org/10.5032/jae.2014.01106>
- Fordyce, Stacey. "Improving Student Engagement through Self- Regulated Learning: A Literature Review." *BU Journal of Graduate Studies in Education*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2024, p. 2024. Accessed 2 Oct. 2025.
- Foxworthy, W. Alex, and William McCarter. "Uncovering the Treasure of Self-Directed Learning." *Inquiry: The Journal of the Virginia Community Colleges*, vol. 28, no. 1, 7 Apr. 2025, p. 28. Accessed 2 Oct. 2025.
- Furlong, M., Smith, D., Springer, T., & Dowdy, E. (2021). Bored with School! Bored with Life? Well-Being Characteristics Associated with a School Boredom Mindset. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 2021, 1–21. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED612166.pdf>
- Goel, M. (2024). *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Education and Research*. <https://multieducationjournal.com/assets/archives/2024/vol9issue1/9020.pdf>
- Goodenow, C. (1993). The psychological sense of school membership among adolescents: Scale development and educational correlates. *Psychology in the Schools*, 30(1), 79–90.
- Laing, G. (2020). The Educational Triage Model. *Journal of Business Education & Scholarship of Teaching*, 14(1), 79–89. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1276540.pdf>
- McGuire, S. Y. (2021). Close the Metacognitive Equity Gap: Teach All Students How to Learn. *Journal of College Academic Support Programs*, 4(1), 69–72. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1350002>

- Mitani, H. (2021). Test score gaps in higher order thinking skills: Exploring instructional practices to improve the skills and narrow the gaps. *AERA Open*, 7(1), 233285842110164. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584211016470>
- Pan, Y.-C. (2024). A Work-Based Approach for Improving Students' Performance in the College General English Class. *English Language Teaching Educational Journal*, 7(2), 65–78. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1454536>
- Peconcillo Jr, L. B., D. Peteros, E., O. Mamites, I., T. Sanchez, D., L. Tenerife, J. J. J. J., & L. Suson, R. (2020). Structuring Determinants to Level Up Students Performance. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 8(4), 638–651. <https://doi.org/10.18488/journal.61.2020.84.638.651>
- Sharma, Gitima, and Mariya Yukhymenko-Lescroart. "High School Students' Subjective Well-Being: The Role of Life Purpose and Academic Identity." *Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies in Education*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2023, pp. 1–22. Accessed 2 Oct. 2025.
- Voelkl (1997). *Identification with School*. (2025). Ets.org. https://www.ets.org/research/policy_research_reports/publications/article/1997/hnll.html
- West, S. (2024). Overcoming Student Apathy Through Innovative Technology, Engagement, and Social-Emotional Strategies. *Journal of Instructional Research*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.9743/jir.2024.13.6>
- Yacek, D. W., & Jonas, M. E. (2020). The Problem of Student Disengagement: Struggle, Escapism and Nietzsche's Birth of Tragedy. *Philosophical Inquiry in Education*, 26(1), 64–87. <https://doi.org/10.7202/1071421ar>

Appendices

Appendix A	DOTS Survey
Appendix B	Proctor Script
Appendix C	Data Results
Appendix D	Raw Data

1. My education will create many future opportunities for me.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

5. I feel like I have a say about what happens to me at school.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

2. If I get confused or very behind in a class, I just quit trying.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

6. I make the decisions about the classes I take and my plans for after high school.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

3. Grades are a good reflection of how smart people are.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

7. Some of my classes challenge me to think about new ideas and form my own opinions.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

4. PHS assignments and tests do a good job measuring my abilities.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

8. The skills I learn here will help me achieve success in the future.

- 1
Strongly Disagree
- 2
Disagree
- 3
Agree
- 4
Strongly Agree

Disengagement Observation

Tracking Survey (DOTS)

Circle the correct response for each question:

1. I am a: MALE FEMALE

2. My overall GPA is:

- Below 1.5
- 1.5 to 2.5
- 2.5 to 3.5
- 3.5+

3. Most school years I am absent:

- 5 days or less
- 5 to 10 days
- 10 to 15 days
- 15+ days

4. I am a:

- Freshman
- Sophomore
- Junior
- Senior

Appendix B: Proctor Script

As some of you may already know, the level of student apathy (also known as “indifference” or “not caring”) has increased in the past decade. We are here today to see what correlations can be made between your answers from this study and others that are similar. Your participation in this survey will help us to better understand what causes students to feel disengaged in school.

This survey is anonymous, which means you will not be asked for any personally identifiable information. There are no wrong answers, so don't be afraid to answer honestly.

Please do not skip questions. If a question doesn't apply to you, try to answer it to the best of your ability. If you feel stuck or confused, raise your hand and someone will come around to help you.

Those of you interested in participating in our study please raise your hand to receive a survey. Once you are given a survey you may begin.

After you are finished, please bring your survey to one of us and we will put it in the folder.

Questions, comments, or concerns?

Does anyone have any questions before we begin?

Appendix C

90% (83/92) believe education creates future opportunities

SO, 10% of PHS students see no future value in getting an education

THIS CORRELATES WITH QUESTION 8:

91% (84/92) believe the skills they learn at PHS will lead to success later

30% (28/92) say they quit trying when they are confused or behind in class

So, 1 in 3 students who is confused or behind quits trying

The majority of these students (approx. 80%) self-reported a GPA of 2.5 or lower

27% (25/92) believe good grades = how smart a person is

SO, 75% of students do not see grades as a valid measure of intelligence

90% (22/25) of students who believe grades = smart self reported a GPA of 3.5+

39% (36/92) believe tests and assignments measure their abilities well

SO, 60% of students feel their talents and abilities are not well measured by school

49% (45/92) feel PHS seeks and considers their personal input about decisions

SO, half of PHS students feel their input is not wanted or considered

74% (68/92) say classes challenge them to think and form new opinions

SO, a quarter of the student body feel unchallenged by their coursework

Average	3.589628	1.864009	3.322678	2.055341	2.159288	2.37291	2.485217	3.18808	3.002245	2.97082
10	F	4	2	4	2	2	2	2	3	4
10	F	3	2	4	2	3	4	3	3	3
10	F	4	1	4	2	2	3	2	3	3
10	F	3	1	4	1	2	2	4	2	2
10	F	4	4	4	1	2	3	4	3	4
10	F	4	2	3	1	2	1	3	3	3
10	F	4	1	3	1	2	2	3	4	3
10	F	3	4	2	2	3	1	3	3	3
10	F	3	4	4	3	2	4	4	4	3
10	F	3	2	4	3	3	3	4	3	3
10	F	3	2	4	2	2	4	3	3	3
10	F	3	2	3	1	2	4	3	3	3
10	F	3	2	3	3	2	2	4	2	2
10	F	3	2	3	3	2	1	3	4	3

Average	3.472098	2.074899	3.32179	2.115508	2.089229	2.320653	2.331207	3.287087	2.974654	2.857278
10	M	1	4	3	2	2	4	4	4	4
10	M	4	1	3	1	3	3	3	3	3
10	M	3	2	4	2	3	3	4	3	3
10	M	4	1	3	1	3	4	3	1	3
10	M	3	3	3	4	3	2	3	2	3
10	M	3	2	4	1	2	3	4	3	3
10	M	3	2	3	2	4	1	3	3	3
10	M	4	2	4	3	3	2	4	3	3
10	M	4	2	3	2	2	3	3	3	3
10	M	3	2	4	2	3	2	3	3	3
10	M	3	2	4	2	2	2	4	3	3
10	M	4	2	4	4	2	1	4	3	3
10	M	3	1	3	2	3	2	3	3	2
10	M	4	1	3	2	3	2	3	3	2

Average	3.313781	2.002774	3.345251	2.004278	2.114416	2.45632	2.493748	3.381003	2.999061	2.994714
9	F	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	2
9	F	3	4	3	1	2	1	2	3	4
9	F	3	1	3	3	2	2	3	2	2
9	F	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	3	3
9	F	3	4	3	3	1	3	3	2	2
9	F	2	1	3	2	3	3	4	3	3
9	F	3	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	3
9	F	4	2	4	3	3	2	4	3	3
9	F	4	4	3	2	3	4	3	2	3

Average	3.216274	2.085491	3.268529	2.114438	2.061212	2.438249	2.439582	3.324114	2.888159	2.912555
9	M	2	2	3	4	2	2	3	3	3
9	M	3	2	3	4	1	3	4	2	2
9	M	3	3	4	2	3	3	4	3	4
9	M	4	1	4	1	3	3	3	3	2
9	M	4	2	3	1	2	2	4	1	4
9	M	4	1	4	1	3	3	3	3	3
9	M	3	2	3	1	3	1	3	3	3
9	M	3	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
9	M	4	1	3	2	3	3	3	3	3
9	M	4	1	3	1	3	3	3	3	3

Average	9	M	3	2	3	1	2	3	3	3	3	3
	3.160814	2.004275	3.163426	2.205722	2.003061	2.471912	2.471979	3.216206	2.644408	2.895628		